

ATM

System Description:

The ATM allows you to withdraw money from your bank account using a credit card.

System Requirements:

The ATM must eject the card if it is blocked.

The ATM must allow three PIN entry attempts before blocking the card and reset the PIN attempt counter to three after a successful PIN entry.

The ATM must allow the user to enter a withdrawal amount after successful PIN entry.

The ATM must eject the card and not dispense bills if the account has insufficient funds.

The ATM must eject the card and wait for it to be removed before dispensing bills upon a successful withdrawal and the ATM must return to standby mode after the user collects the dispensed bills.

The ATM must allow the user to cancel the transaction when the ATM is waiting for an input for a PIN.

The ATM must allow the user to cancel the transaction when the ATM is waiting for an input for an amount.

The ATM must eject the card if the transaction is canceled.

Model Test Purpose with keywords:

In dot format

The ATM must eject the card if it is blocked.

PMTP:

```
digraph Automaton {  
  S0 [shape=octagon];  
  S1 [shape=circle];  
  S1 -> S1 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important  
  S0 -> S1 [label="ejectBlockedCard", style=solid]; // Blocked card ejected  
  S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\\ejectBlockedCard", style=solid]; // Not important  
}
```


NMTP:

```
digraph Automaton {  
  S1 [shape=circle];  
  S0 [shape=octagon];
```

```

S2 [shape=circle];
S0 -> S1 [label="insertBlockedCard", style=solid]; // Blocked card inserted
S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\insertBlockedCard", style=solid]; // Not important
S1 -> S2 [label="pinok", style=dashed]; // Pin entered after a blocked card is inserted
S2 -> S2 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\pinok", style=solid]; // Not important
}

```

The ATM must allow three PIN entry attempts before blocking the card and reset the PIN attempt counter to three after a successful PIN entry.

PMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
S1 [shape=circle];
S2 [shape=circle];
S3 [shape=circle];
S0 [shape=octagon];
S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\pinko2", style=solid]; // Not important
S3 -> S3 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
S2 -> S3 [label="pinko3", style=solid]; // 3rd incorrect PIN attempt, card blocked
S2 -> S0 [label="Σ\pinko3", style=solid]; // Not important
S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\pinko1", style=solid]; // Not important
S0 -> S1 [label="pinko1", style=solid]; // 1st incorrect PIN attempt
S1 -> S2 [label="pinko2", style=solid]; // 2nd incorrect PIN attempt
}

```


NMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
  S2 [shape=circle];
  S3 [shape=circle];
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S4 [shape=circle];
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\enterWrongPIN", style=solid]; // Not important
  S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\enterWrongPIN", style=solid]; // Not important
  S1 -> S2 [label="enterWrongPIN", style=solid]; // Enter wrong PIN 2nd attempt
  S4 -> S4 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S1 [label="enterWrongPIN", style=solid]; // Enter wrong PIN 1st attempt
  S3 -> S4 [label="enterWrongPIN", style=dashed]; // Enter wrong PIN 4th attempt, but it
  // should stop at the 3rd attempt
  S3 -> S0 [label="Σ\enterWrongPIN", style=solid]; // Not important
  S2 -> S0 [label="Σ\enterWrongPIN", style=solid]; // Not important
  S2 -> S3 [label="enterWrongPIN", style=solid]; // Enter wrong PIN 3rd attempt
}

```


The ATM must allow the user to enter a withdrawal amount after successful PIN entry.

PMTF:

```

digraph Automaton {
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S2 [shape=circle];
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S1 -> S0 [label="\Sigma\enterAmount", style=solid]; // Not important
  S2 -> S2 [label="\Sigma", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S0 [label="\Sigma\pinok", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S1 [label="pinok", style=solid]; // PIN correct
  S1 -> S2 [label="enterAmount", style=solid]; // Amount entered
}
  
```


NMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S2 [shape=circle];
  S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\enterWrongPIN", style=solid]; // Not important
  S2 -> S2 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S1 [label="enterWrongPIN", style=solid]; // Wrong PIN entered
  S1 -> S2 [label="enterAmount", style=dashed]; // Amount entered after a wrong PIN attempt,
  this shouldn't be possible
  S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\enterAmount", style=solid]; // Not important
}

```



```

digraph Automaton {
S1 [shape=circle];
S0 [shape=octagon];
S2 [shape=circle];
S0 -> S1 [label="insertCard", style=solid]; // Card inserted
S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\enterAmount", style=solid]; // Not important
S2 -> S2 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
S1 -> S2 [label="enterAmount", style=dashed]; // Amount entered after a card is inserted,
this shouldn't be possible
S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\insertCard", style=solid]; // Not important
}

```

The ATM must eject the card and not dispense bills if the account has insufficient funds.

PMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
S2 [shape=circle];
S1 [shape=circle];
S0 [shape=octagon];
S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\insufficientFunds", style=solid]; // Not important
S2 -> S2 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\ ejectCardInsufficientFunds", style=solid]; // insufficient funds entered
S1 -> S2 [label="ejectCardInsufficientFunds", style=solid]; // insufficient funds entered
S0 -> S1 [label="insufficientFunds", style=solid]; // insufficient funds entered
}

```


NMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S2 [shape=circle];
  S3 [shape=circle];
  S1 -> S2 [label="ejectCardInsufficientFunds", style=solid]; // Card ejected because of
insuffisent funds
  S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\ ejectCardInsufficientFunds", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S1 [label="insufficientFunds", style=solid]; // Insuffisent funds
  S2 -> S3 [label="collectBills", style=dashed]; // Bills dispensed but there is insuffisent funds,
this shouldn't be possible
  S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\insufficientFunds", style=solid]; // Not important
  S3 -> S3 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
  S2 -> S0 [label="Σ\collectBills", style=solid]; // Not important
}
  
```


The ATM must eject the card and wait for it to be removed before dispensing bills upon a successful withdrawal and the ATM must return to standby mode after the user collects the dispensed bills.

PMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
  S2 [shape=circle];
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S3 [shape=circle];
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S1 -> S2 [label="removeCardForDispense", style=solid]; // Remove card and dispense bills
  S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\removeCardForDispense", style=solid]; // Not important
  S2 -> S3 [label="collectBills", style=solid]; // Collect bills
  S2 -> S0 [label="Σ\collectBills", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S1 [label="ejectCardBeforeDispensing", style=solid]; // Successful withdrawal
  S3 -> S3 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\ejectCardBeforeDispensing", style=solid]; // Not important
}
  
```


NMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S2 [shape=circle];
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\collectBills", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S1 [label="ejectCardBeforeDispensing", style=solid]; // successful withdrawal
  S1 -> S2 [label="collectBills", style=dashed]; // Bills collected just after a successful
  withdrawal, this shouldn't be possible
  S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\ ejectCardBeforeDispensing", style=solid]; // Not important
  S2 -> S2 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
}
  
```



```

digraph Automaton {
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S2 [shape=circle];
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S3 [shape=circle];
  S4 [shape=circle];
  S2 -> S3 [label="collectBills", style=solid]; // Bills collected
  S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\removeCardForDispense", style=solid]; // Not important
  S2 -> S0 [label="Σ\collectBills", style=solid]; // Not important
  S3 -> S0 [label="Σ\enterAmount", style=solid]; // Not important
  S3 -> S4 [label="enterAmount", style=dashed]; // Entered amount after bills collected, this
  shouldn't be possible
  S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\ ejectCardBeforeDispensing", style=solid]; // Not important
  S4 -> S4 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S1 [label="ejectCardBeforeDispensing", style=solid]; // Successful withdrawal
  S1 -> S2 [label="removeCardForDispense", style=solid]; // Card removed
}

```


The ATM must allow the user to cancel the transaction when the ATM is waiting for an input for a PIN.

PMTF:

```

digraph Automaton {
  S2 [shape=circle];
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S0 -> S1 [label="insertCard", style=solid]; // Card inserted
  S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\insertCard", style=solid]; // Not important
  S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\cancelFromPin", style=solid]; // Not important
  S1 -> S2 [label="cancelFromPin", style=solid]; // Transaction cancelled from PIN entry
  S2 -> S2 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
}

```


NMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
  S2 [shape=circle];
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\enterAmount", style=solid]; // Not important
  S2 -> S2 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S1 [label="enterAmount", style=solid]; // Amount entered
  S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\cancelFromAmount AND cancelFromPin", style=solid]; // Not important
  S1 -> S2 [label="cancelFromPin AND cancelFromAmount", style=dashed]; // Cancel after
  amount entered, this shouldn't be possible
}
  
```


The ATM must allow the user to cancel the transaction when the ATM is waiting for an input for a PIN.

PMTP:

```
digraph Automaton {
  S2 [shape=circle];
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S2 -> S2 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
  S1 -> S2 [label="cancelFromAmount", style=solid]; // Transaction cancelled from amount
  entry
  S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\pinok", style=solid]; // Not important
  S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\cancelFromAmount", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S1 [label="pinok", style=solid]; // PIN correct
}
```


The ATM must eject the card if the transaction is canceled.

PMTP:

```
digraph Automaton {
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S2 [shape=circle];
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\jectCard", style=solid]; // Not important
```

```

S2 -> S2 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
S0 -> S1 [label="cancelFromPin", style=solid]; // Transaction cancelled from PIN entry
S0 -> S1 [label="cancelFromAmount", style=solid]; // Transaction cancelled from amount
entry
S1 -> S2 [label="ejectCard", style=solid]; // Eject card after cancellation
S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\cancelFromAmount OR cancelFromPin", style=solid]; // Not important
}

```


NMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
S0 [shape=octagon];
S1 [shape=circle];
S2 [shape=circle];
S0 -> S1 [label="cancelFromAmount AND cancelFromPin", style=solid]; // Cancel
S1 -> S2 [label="pinok", style=dashed]; // PIN entered after cancelation, this shouldn't be
possible
S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\cancelFromAmount AND cancelFromPin", style=solid]; // Not important
S2 -> S2 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
S1 -> S0 [label="Σ\pinok", style=solid]; // Not important
}

```

Prompt for model in ModelJUnit generation:

You are a professional tester specialized in Model-Based Testing.

Generate an FSM in ModelJUnit

System Description:

The ATM allows you to withdraw money from your bank account using a credit card.

System Requirements:

The ATM must eject the card if it is blocked.

The ATM must allow three PIN entry attempts before blocking the card and reset the PIN attempt counter to three after a successful PIN entry.

The ATM must allow the user to enter a withdrawal amount after successful PIN entry.

The ATM must eject the card and not dispense bills if the account has insufficient funds.

The ATM must eject the card and wait for it to be removed before dispensing bills upon a successful withdrawal and the ATM must return to standby mode after the user collects the dispensed bills.

The ATM must allow the user to cancel the transaction when the ATM is waiting for an input for a PIN.

The ATM must allow the user to cancel the transaction when the ATM is waiting for an input for an amount.

Instructions:

States are represented as a group of variables.

Actions the system can perform are transitions between states.

Specify the state variables that influence transitions.

Identify guards (conditions for actions to execute).

Define the roles/users involved.

ModelJUnit-Specific Instructions:

Use @Action for transitions and they must have no parameters.

Guards should be methods named [actionName]Guard() (e.g., loginGuard() for login()).

Example of an action with a guard:

```
...  
  
public boolean actionName1Guard() {  
    return stateVar1 == true && stateVar2 != 3;  
}  
@Action  
public void action1Name() {  
    stateVar3 = false;  
}  
public boolean actionName2Guard() {  
    return stateVar2 < 3 && stateVar3 == true;  
}  
@Action  
public void action2Name() {  
    stateVar2 = 5;  
}  
...
```

The model must implement FsmModel with getState() and reset(boolean testing).

Track state variables (e.g., boolean, int) to control transitions.

Additional Requests:

- Class must be named "ModelGenerated".

- Ensure all states are reachable.

- Ensure all transitions have proper guards.

- Model error cases (e.g., invalid inputs).

- Include role-based access control if applicable.

- Optimize for test coverage (e.g., edge cases).

Some actions are not valid in all states, so you can add a guard method to say when that action is enabled. It must have no parameters and must return a boolean. The action method will only be called when its guard is true

- No explanation is needed, just the code